

AERODYNAMIC CLOCKING ASSOCIATED WITH COMPRESSOR INLET CONDITIONS AND ITS EFFECT ON EMBEDDED ROTOR FORCED RESPONSE

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ABSTRACT

Unsteady blade loading in a multistage compressor is influenced by the aerodynamic interactions of the upstream and downstream blade rows. Researchers aim to acquire measurements in the multistage environment to better understand these interactions. To achieve repeatable aerodynamic performance, research facilities that operate with unconditioned ambient air apply corrections to rotational shaft speed and mass flow rate based on the ratio of inlet flow conditions to standard-day reference conditions. This approach was utilized when measuring the vibratory response of the embedded rotor on different days. Despite correcting to standard day conditions prior to the mechanical speed sweeps used to capture the vibratory data, the different ambient conditions lead to more than a 30% change in blade responses.

The objective of this research is to investigate why the variation in ambient conditions had such a significant impact on the measured forced response of the embedded rotor and explores the mechanisms that affect unsteady loading. Experimental measurements supplemented by CFD results provide detailed insights into the aerodynamic interactions between the stages of the multistage compressor. The computed drop in modal force matched the experimental measurements within 1.5%, indicating the main drivers were captured by the CFD. Numerical clocking studies corresponding to the inlet conditions reveal a reduction in the mean response level, accompanied by a phase shift in the sinusoidal response between different clocking cases.

Thus, the variations in ambient conditions result in (i) changes in blade loading and (ii) aerodynamic clocking due to the variations in the incidence angle and in the timing of wake and potential field impingement on the rotor. These variations alter the forced response behavior of the embedded rotor significantly in these experiments. Such effects are most pronounced in multistage compressors with identical upstream and downstream vane counts with strong clocking effects.

Keywords: Forced Response, Unsteady Aerodynamics, Tip Timing

NOMENCLATURE

α	absolute flow angle
k_z	axial wave number
k_r	radial wave number
\dot{m}_c	Corrected mass flow rate
1T	First torsion mode
CWB	Chordwise Bending Mode
DSR	Deflection-Stress ratio
EO	Engine Order
G5, G6	Test Datasets
HL	High Loading
IGV	Inlet guide vane
MF	Modal Force
M_ϕ	Circumferential Mach number
M_z	Axial Mach number
NSMS	Non-Intrusive Stress Measurement System
OPR	once-per-revolution
PE	Peak Efficiency
RANS	Reynolds Navier Stokes Equations
vp	Vane passage
TC	Tip clearance

1. INTRODUCTION

Advancements in engine design, with closely spaced blade rows in multistage compressors, lead to increased blade-row interactions. These interactions necessitate a comprehensive understanding of the underlying physics, with a particular focus on aero-structural interactions and rotor forced-response vibrations. Factors influencing forced response include rotor-stator interactions related to blade counts, vane clocking, structural damping, mistuning, and operating conditions. The primary sources of unsteady pressure distribution are the viscous wakes shed by the upstream blade row and the potential disturbances generated by adjacent blade rows. An early

analytical study on unsteady forces by Kemp and Sears [1] used a viscous wake model to approximate the unsteady effects experienced by the blade row passing through the viscous wake.

The superposition of the upstream and downstream influences drives the amplitude and frequency of a blade's pressure fluctuation. As a result, the aerodynamic interactions in a multistage compressor strongly depend on the vane counts and the relative circumferential position of upstream and downstream rows, also known as vane clocking. Over the years, several studies have focused on measuring and analyzing vortical and potential distortions to investigate these interactions further [2–7]. Li and He [8] studied various configurations and found that a specific blade count configuration exhibited aperiodic circumferential forcing with a variation of approximately three times the magnitude. Their findings indicated that both circumferential clocking and blade count selection could effectively control the maximum stator blade response. Even though the adjacent upstream and downstream vane rows have the strongest influence on the unsteady pressure of a blade row, subsequent research also identified influences from other upstream and downstream blade rows [9].

In recent years, the effects of vane clocking on the performance and resonant response of the rotor have been widely investigated, including research focused on separating the upstream and downstream influences [10–14]. Initial numerical studies on the unsteady forces associated with vane clocking [15] demonstrated that higher pressure amplitudes corresponded to clocking positions with higher efficiencies. Smith and Key [16] studied the effect of the vane clocking effects on the downstream stator vane losses. Wake convection, which affects performance and downstream stator losses, was significantly impacted by the loading condition due to resulting changes in velocities and flow angles. The wake of the upstream stator alters the inlet relative flow angle of the rotor, resulting in increased circulation and loading of the blade. This increased loading could be further increased or reduced by the time of interaction with the potential field. Müller et al. [17] studied this mechanism, illustrated in Figure 1. They observed that the LE clocking configuration, where wake impingement and potential field interaction occur simultaneously, exhibited higher loading than the MID configuration, where the wake is near mid-chord when the potential field influences the trailing edge.

Choi et al. [18] quantified the effects of steady loading and vane clocking on rotor resonant response, showing a significant variation in the forced response for the same compressor in the present study. This compressor showed strong clocking effects, with the maximum difference of mean response amplitudes across six vane clocking configurations being 80% at design loading and 168% at high loading. The difference was attributed to the phasing of the potential field from Stators 1 and 2, as there was a very small variation in the Stator 1 wake profile associated with vane clocking. While compressors of similar vane counts are not common in the field, they are a useful research tool. When vane counts are similar, a true area-averaged flow field can be measured by traversing across only one vane row. Also, adjusting the circumferential placement of a particular vane row

will modify the blade row interactions in a uniform manner around the entire annulus.

Figure 1: Flow Field in the third stage for clocking configurations a) MID and b) LE [17]

While clocking affects the phasing of the upstream and downstream potential fields, rotor unsteady loading is also affected when the rotor chops through the wakes shed from the upstream stator. Niu et al. [19] observed a reduction in the flow angle and localized acceleration zone on the rotor suction surface due to the negative jet effects of the upstream stator. The localized zone was affected by the stator wake and the separation between the wakes, and it is referred to as wake reduced frequency in their study. This acceleration zone weakened in the case of high reduced frequency flows due to the reduced pressure gradient of the wake transport fluid and the bulk flow. These localized zones can influence the fluctuating pressure on the blades.

The mechanisms affecting the unsteady pressure distribution of a compressor blade are summarized as follows by Mailach et al. [11]:

- 1) The potential disturbances from the upstream and downstream blade rows;
- 2) Impingement of wakes, which changes the blade circulation; and
- 3) The chopped-wake segments linked with the negative jet effect convect along the blade surfaces.

Rotor forced response studies often use non-intrusive measurement systems to capture vibratory data, supplemented by strain gauge measurements. Usually, vibratory data is collected for different loading conditions and rotational speed sweep rates. These loading conditions are maintained at steady-state corrected speeds along a designated speed line to ensure a consistent dataset. A speed sweep through the resonant

mechanical speed range is then performed to gather comprehensive datasets of the forced response without subjecting the blades to a sustained resonant condition. However, facilities using unconditioned atmospheric air are subject to changes in the flow field due to inherent variations in ambient conditions such as pressure, temperature, and humidity. These facilities use corrections to reference inlet conditions to achieve the same pressure rise and match the flow fields between different days and ambient conditions. Smith et al. [20] took detailed measurements over 12 months, demonstrating these effects can be significant and that subtle changes in the experimental setup can cause measurable differences in the flow field and compressor performance.

Despite correcting for standard day inlet conditions at a steady-state operating point on the compressor map, the transient sweeps through the mechanical speeds for resonant forced response studies under different inlet conditions can correspond to different corrected conditions on the compressor map, or different flow Mach numbers. This discrepancy can significantly influence the vibratory response of the rotor, depending on the configuration.

This paper investigates the superimposed effects of the slight variations in the upstream and downstream influences on the forced response of the embedded rotor. The interaction is significant in compressors with identical upstream and downstream vane counts, as is the case in the present study. Particular emphasis is placed on the factors contributing to variations in unsteady pressure distributions across the blade surfaces, which in turn influence the modal forces. These findings provide critical insight into the importance of inlet variations and loading conditions on forced response behavior, thereby contributing to the advancement of more robust and reliable aero-engine designs.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental datasets were obtained in the Purdue 3-Stage (P3S) Axial Compressor Research facility, shown in Figure 2. This compressor represents the rear stages of a high-pressure compressor, with engine-representative Mach and Reynolds numbers. The compressor is designed to operate at 5,000 rpm and is geometrically scaled up to accommodate inter-blade row instrumentation while minimizing significant blockage effects. The ambient air is drawn through a large settling chamber, followed by an ASME standard long-form venturi and an elliptical nosecone, which directs the air into the 2-inch annular test section. The compressor has a constant annulus with a hub-to-tip ratio of 0.833 and a hub radius of 10 inches. Further details on the facility can be found in Kormanik et al [21].

The flowpath is illustrated in Figure 3. The compressor test section includes an inlet guide vane (IGV) followed by three stages, using NACA 65-series airfoil designs for the stators and double circular arc designs for both the IGV and rotor blades. The vane rows are individually indexable, with positions measured by precision string potentiometers, enabling pitchwise traverses past stationary instrumentation and also enabling vane

clocking studies. The baseline configuration consists of 44 vanes for all vane rows except for Stator 3, which has a vane count of 50. The rotor counts are 36, 33, and 30 blades for Rotor 1, Rotor 2, and Rotor 3, respectively.

Figure 2: Purdue Three-Stage Axial Compressor Research Facility

Figure 3: Flowpath with measurement station location

Seven-element Kiel-head rakes are used to measure P_o and T_o at ten interstage axial locations (Stations 0-9 in Figure 3), along with casing static pressures at four circumferential locations. To avoid any potential additional excitations, the interstage rakes from station 2 to station 7 were removed during the forced response studies. The vibratory response of the embedded rotor is acquired with eight Agilis Non-intrusive Stress Measurement System (NSMS) probes installed over the rotor blade tips located in a 60-degree sector of the casing. The axial location of the NSMS probes was optimized using the computed tip deflection from a modal analysis using Ansys Mechanical to capture first torsion (1T), first chordwise bending (1CWB), and second chordwise bending mode (2CWB) modes. The circumferential probe locations were optimized using single-mode fitting for each mode. The tip timing probes for the rotor were installed at approximately 0.055 inches (1.397 mm or 2% chord) from the trailing edge.

The NSMS is limited in its ability to accurately capture complex vibratory responses for both small tip deflections and overlapping modes from multiple engine orders. These limitations arise from both its post-processing methodology and circumferential measurement location. To address these shortcomings, the GUIDE VI experimental campaign was supplemented with strain gauge instrumentation, which enables continuous monitoring of blade vibrations. The placements of the strain gauges were optimized to capture the modes and nodal diameter (ND) of interest. Eight R2 blades were instrumented with three Micro Measurements ED-DY-031CF-350 strain gauges. The data acquisition was time synchronized, with circumferential blade tracking from a one-per-revolution (OPR) signal aligned to blade one.

2.1 Experimental Results

The vibratory datasets were acquired in two experimental campaigns, GUIde V and GUIde VI, on days with substantially different ambient conditions. The engine order (EO) crossings acquired for these campaigns are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: EO crossings

Mechanical Speed	Mode of Excitation
3400 RPM	88EO - 1CWB
3700 RPM	44EO - 1T

The loading conditions for the speed sweeps were set at 68% corrected speed. The calculated differences between the experiments for the corrected mass flow rate and TPR were 0.34% and 0.6%, respectively, representing a good match of loading conditions for the two test campaigns. Despite matching the operating point at 68% corrected speed, a discrepancy in the vibratory response measured in the transient sweeps of the resonant conditions was profound. The peak-to-peak deflection amplitude and frequency of the embedded rotor are shown in Figure 4. A reduction of 5.5 mils, corresponding to about 35.2% of the mean amplitude of the response, was observed for the high loading, 1st Torsion (HL-1T) crossing, along with a shift in the mean frequency.

Figure 4: 44EO – 1T (HL): Maximum blade response (top) and peak response blade frequency (bottom) for GUIde V and GUIde VI

Additionally, the datasets from different days in the two test campaigns were compared at the peak efficiency (PE) loading condition. The peak-to-peak deflection and peak frequency for the PE loading case are shown in Figure 5. The comparison of this case reveals a smaller difference, of approximately 6%, in the mean amplitude, along with a slight frequency shift. Notably,

the difference in the inlet total temperature for the two campaigns at the PE case was only about one-third of the difference at the HL case. The difference in total temperature and pressure at station 0 for HL and PE cases presented in this study are given in Table 2.

Figure 5: 44EO – 1T (PE): Maximum blade response (top) and peak response blade frequency (bottom) for GUIde V and GUIde VI

Table 2: Differences in the ambient conditions between GUIde V and GUIde VI cases

Case	Condition in GUIde V – Condition in GUIde VI	
	ΔP_o [psi]	ΔT_o [F]
PE	-0.024	-10.54
HL	+0.095	-27.96

The installation of the strain gauges for GUIde VI included a complete rebuild of the rotor assembly. With the NSMS probes installed in the casing, a potential axial shift in the measurement location is considered and investigated to determine its role in the change in the responses. The axial shift is computed by correlating the blade thickness measured by NSMS with the tip deflection calculated using modal analysis. The mode of interest and the tip deflection of the normalized torsion mode, as well as the blade thickness, are determined using the blade profile data, shown in Figure 6. The shift in the axial location of the experimental measurement location is then calculated using the measured thickness and the correlated location.

The blade thickness calculated from the NSMS measurements for both test campaigns is shown in Figure 7. An increase of approximately 6.7 mils in the mean blade thickness is observed, corresponding to an axial shift of 0.032 inches,

which would result in a 2.3% decrease in the measured deflection amplitude for the 1T mode.

Figure 6: Torsional Mode (top) and Measured blade thickness and normalised mode shape (1T) (bottom)

Figure 7: Blade thickness computed using NSMS data

After accounting for the axial shift of the rotor between the two test campaigns, the experimental data still showed a 32.9% difference in the measured response amplitudes for the HL case. With the only significant difference between the campaigns being the ambient inlet conditions for the HL case, this effect was explored further using computational fluid dynamics (CFD).

3. COMPUTATIONAL SETUP

This study employs CFD to analyze the unsteady three-dimensional flow field of the Purdue 3-stage axial compressor in detail, supplementing the experimental data with important insights. The computational domain encompasses all blade rows,

which are spatially discretized using Ansys TurboGrid. A non-conformal mesh at the rotor tip requires the use of an interpolating interface. The numerical model in this study excludes the stator cavities and bleed secondary flow paths and considers a cold tip clearance (TC) of 1.5%. The flow within the stator cavities is often complex, and modeling them is often associated with a significant increase in computational cost. The adverse effects resulting from interactions between the main flow and hub leakage flow of this compressor were investigated in detail in a previous study [22]. While these approaches account for important secondary flow aerodynamics, this study focuses on aeromechanics and the modal force of the torsional mode with considerable rotor blade tip displacement. The current approach reduces grid size by excluding cavity geometries, addressing major constraints that significantly increase computational cost and modeling complexity. The variations in the tip clearances between cold and hot days and their effects on the performance were quantified in an earlier study [20]. However, due to the transient nature of this study with long speed sweeps, the tip clearances are assumed to be constant.

3.1 Simulation Methodology

ANSYS CFX-5 2024 R2, a commercial finite-volume-based solver, is utilized to numerically solve the Navier–Stokes equations. The RANS and URANS models were developed using the SST turbulence model, including curvature correction for turbulence closure [23,24]. The low temperature rise of the compressor supports the assumption that the working fluid may be adequately treated as an ideal gas. The total energy equation is used to model the heat transfer in the fluid domain, accounting for both convective transport and viscous work contributions.

The computational domain used for this study is shown in Figure 8. The inlet and outlet boundaries extend slightly beyond the region illustrated in the figure. The steady-state model utilizes mixing plane interfaces to account for changes in pitch and reference frame between the domains. For the transient simulations, the mixing plane interfaces between S1-R2 and R2-S2 are replaced with Time Transformation (TT) interfaces based on Giles’ time-inclination method [25]. The strongest influences on the embedded rotor unsteady pressure distribution are its neighboring blade rows, which have, therefore, been included in the unsteady computational domain. Modeling the unsteady domain with 4-3-4 passages yields a pitch ratio of unity for both TT interfaces.

Figure 8: Computational Domain

The inlet boundary conditions are set using the experimental measurements of total pressure and total temperature acquired at station 0. The exit-corrected mass flow rate is held constant between cases for each loading condition. To simulate a throttle line or operating line in most compressor applications, a fixed exit corrected mass flow rate is used with varying rotational speed [25]. Although the experimental data for this compressor indicate that the exit corrected mass flow rate changes slightly during speed sweeps, for the cases in the current study, it has been assumed to be constant due to the lack of continuous monitoring of the performance data during the sweeps for earlier tests. Each blade passing of Rotor 2 is resolved with 99 timesteps, which translates to about 0.11° of the full revolution per timestep.

The variation in ambient conditions alters the exit flow angles and, along with variations in Mach numbers, effectively introduces “aerodynamic clocking” to the flow since it causes a change in the phase of the upstream and downstream forcing functions. A method for investigating and validating the aerodynamic clocking phenomenon involves comparing responses across multiple physical clocking conditions for the inlet conditions from both campaigns. An additional computational clocking study is used to further investigate this aerodynamic clocking. Stator 2 is clocked relative to Stator 1 at five equally spaced discrete locations for this investigation. The clocking configuration is determined by the difference in the vane passage (vp) locations of Stator-1 and Stator-2. In the current investigation, six configurations CL0, CL1, CL2, CL3, CL4, and CL5 at 0%, 16.67%, 33.3%, 50%, 66.67%, and 83.33% vp, respectively, are considered. The mixing plane interfaces outside of the embedded stage blade rows ensure that the changes in the forced-response influences are isolated to the clocking of Stator 1 and Stator 2.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Steady Flow

Following a grid convergence study, a baseline steady-state CFD simulation was conducted to validate the computational model against experimental performance data at the 100% corrected speed (Nc) design point. Differences between CFD and experimental results of the inlet-corrected mass flow rate and isentropic efficiency are within 0.6%, as shown in Table 3, and comparisons of area-averaged radial stagnation pressure and temperature profiles are presented in Figures 9–10.

Table 3: Comparison of Experimental and CFD results

	Simulation	Experiment	$\Delta\%$
$\dot{m}_c / \dot{m}_{c\text{-design}}$	1.006	1	0.6
$\eta / \eta_{\text{peak}}$	1.005	1	0.5
TPR	1.311	1.32	-0.68
TTR	1.095	1.093	0.2

Figure 9: Comparison of interstage stagnation pressure profiles between experimental and CFD at 100% Nc, Design Point.

Figure 10: Comparison of stagnation temperature profiles between experimental and CFD at 100% Nc, Design Point.

The profiles are normalized by the area-averaged values at STA0-AIP. Differences in the stagnation pressure profiles show the trade-offs associated with geometric simplifications and emphasize the significance of spanwise mixing effects, which are not accurately captured in steady-state CFD simulations.

Conjugate heat transfer studies incorporating solid domains have shown that an accurate thermal boundary can reduce the overprediction of total temperature profiles [26].

Overall, there is a good agreement between the experimental and CFD results, and the main flow was captured well. The differences near the hub are less concerning for this 1-T mode shape, where the maximum deflection is near the tip. The transient CFD runs in the next sections were conducted at 74% (3700 RPM) mechanical speed, corresponding with the resonant crossing of the torsion mode.

4.2 Time-Averaged Pressure Distribution and Unsteady Blade Pressure

The focus now shifts to the high-loading point, where a notable drop in the mean forced response was observed in the second experimental campaign. The periodic-unsteady convergence of the runs is assessed using a method proposed by Clark and Grover [27]. A summary and application of this method is well-documented in a different study of a similar multistage compressor [28]. The flow at high loading is inherently unsteady; therefore, the temporal mean (f_m) of the flow quantities, along with the average blade pressure, was monitored closely for convergence. The overall convergence level was greater than 0.74 for all the cases for frequencies up to the second blade passing. The minimum convergence set level of the method is observed to be the phase of the selected second blade passing frequency component of the signal.

4.3 Loading Effects

The variation in ambient conditions between the two campaigns leads to a slightly different mean flow field, including changes to the incidence angles on the downstream rotor. Figure 11 shows the difference in the time-averaged total pressure of the S1 wake normalized by standard day pressure at 50% span. The only difference between the two cases is the compressor inlet condition, where the GUIde VI case had higher ambient temperatures. The GUIde V wake is deeper compared to the G6 case, along with a shift in the total pressure within the stator passage, indicating a slight change in the loading condition.

Figure 11: Normalised Time-averaged total pressure for the Stator 1 exit flowfield at 50% span.

Spectral analysis of the total pressure profile at 50% span showed a 6.45% reduction in the amplitude corresponding to the 44EO. The variation in ambient conditions also leads to a slight change in the incidence angles of the downstream blade rows, as shown in an exaggerated fashion in Figure 12. The relative flow angle and time-averaged velocity of the S1 wake are shown in Figure 13. The shift in loading and incidence associated with the inlet conditions for these cases is a 2.34° difference in average R2 incidence and a 3.8% difference in axial velocity.

Figure 12: Stator wake velocity triangle

Figure 13: (a) Time-averaged relative flow angle (b) Time-averaged velocity for the Stator 1 exit flowfield at 50% span

Figure 14: Unsteady pressure at the Stator 1 exit for GUIde VI (top) and GUIde V (bottom)

The unsteady Stator 1 exit pressure component corresponding to the 44EO is shown in Figure 14. The pressure level for the GUIde V case is stronger than that of the G6 case. The upstream pressure fluctuations forcing Rotor 2 are, therefore, stronger in the G5 case.

The potential field from Stator 2 (S2) propagates at the same frequency as the upstream disturbances from S1; therefore, a difference in the flow conditions can significantly impact the rotor responses in this case. The axial wave number, k_z , of the flow is mathematically represented using the equation (1) [29], where M_ϕ and M_z are the axial and circumferential Mach numbers, and k_r is the radial wave number. The free acoustic wave number is defined as $k=2\pi f/a$, where f is a function of the pressure distribution in the r - ϕ plane. The sign in the index of $k_{\pm z}$ is always opposite to the sign of M_z . A positive index of $k_{\pm z}$ indicates propagation in the direction of the axial flow, while a negative index indicates propagation against the flow. A negative radical leads to an unsteady pressure wave formulation in that propagates with exponential decay.

$$k_{\pm z} = \frac{\mp M_z(k \pm M_\phi k_r)}{1 - M_z^2} + \frac{\sqrt{(k \pm M_\phi k_r)^2 - (1 - M_z^2)k_r^2}}{1 - M_z^2} \quad (1)$$

The unsteady pressure waves exhibit exponential decay and are strongly dependent on the flow Mach number. The Mach numbers for the GUIde V and GUIde VI campaigns are compared in Figure 15: Time-Averaged Mach number for GUIde VI (top) and GUIde V (bottom) Figure 15. The increased static temperature in the flow field of the GUIde VI case, due to the elevated ambient conditions, leads to a lower local Mach number. Performance studies account for variations in Mach number and flow angles by adjusting the rotational speed, often increasing RPM on hotter days to maintain consistent

aerodynamic conditions or tip Mach numbers. In contrast, forced response studies require the datasets to be collected near the resonant RPM, which prevents such adjustments for tip Mach number due to different inlet temperatures and leads to discrepancies in the resulting flow field.

Figure 15: Time-Averaged Mach number for GUIde VI (top) and GUIde V (bottom) at 50% Span

The computed area-average of the time-averaged Mach number shows a difference of about 2.6% between the cases. Since the axial gap remains constant between the cases, the Mach number controls the time of impingement of the potential field on the rotor blade. This change in the phasing of the interaction between the upstream and downstream pressure disturbances is referred to as aerodynamic clocking in this study. The slight change in the magnitude and phasing of these parameters could lead to significantly different forced response amplitudes for compressors with identical upstream and downstream vane counts.

The normalised stagnation pressure distribution at the Stator 2 exit is shown in Figure 16. The contours are normalised by the area-averaged values at the plane location for qualitative comparison. The scale is adjusted for both cases to highlight the Stator 1 wake, while the extents of the Stator 2 wake are shown in blue. The noticeable shift in pressure deficit corresponding to the Stator 1 wake occurs above the 40% span, indicating a shift in the flow.

Figure 16: Stagnation pressure contours at Stator 2 inlet for G6 (top) and G5 (bottom) cases

A spectral analysis of the pressure field at the S2 inlet showed a 0.48% drop in the amplitude, along with about 0.8° difference in the phase angle corresponding to the 44EO. The upstream and downstream disturbances at the same frequency interact strongly due to the matching vane count, making it difficult to distinguish or separate them. However, their effect on the response can be monitored to understand if the interference was constructive or destructive.

An exaggerated schematic summary of how ambient condition variations affect results is shown in Figure 17. Speedlines $N1_c$ and $N2_c$ represent the corrected speeds corresponding to variations in inlet conditions at the mechanical resonance speed, Figure 17a. The variation in ambient conditions leads to two main aspects: first, changes in the loading, which manifests as a change in the relative flow angle at the rotor inlet; and second, the variation in the Mach number, which affects the propagation of the potential fields and the convective speeds, thereby introducing an aerodynamic clocking, as shown in Figure 17b.

The compressor in this study has strong clocking effects, which were investigated in an earlier study [18]. Small changes in the physical clocking during a particular test led to a big change in the measured responses. Although the physical vane positions remain unchanged in this investigation, the aerodynamic clocking, influenced by the flow conditions, exhibits similar behavior, leading to noticeable variations in the responses.

The time-averaged pressure distribution on the embedded rotor blade at HL is shown in Figure 18. For the GUIde VI case corresponding to a higher ambient temperature, there is a reduced aerodynamic loading accompanied by a shift in rotor incidence.

Figure 17: (a) Variation in the loading (b) Vane clocking

Figure 18: Static pressure distribution on the R2 Blade at 50% span

Figure 19: Normalised unsteady pressure distribution (44EO) at 50% span

The unsteady pressure distribution corresponding to the 44EO is presented in Figure 19, where a significant deviation in pressure profiles is observed. The differences are not just restricted to magnitude. The difference in the profiles is most pronounced between 20% and 80% chord, whereas variations in

magnitude are primarily concentrated near the leading and trailing edges.

The difference in the profiles results from both a reduction in unsteady pressure levels and the effects of aerodynamic clocking, which alters the interaction between disturbances. Some of the differences could also be attributed to the wave reflections from the adjacent rows, which were previously investigated in an earlier study on this compressor [5]. The unsteady pressure was influenced predominantly near the LE and TE, and the change in flow angles could affect these reflections.

4.4 Modal Force

Modal force (MF) quantifies the excitation by unsteady pressure on a specific mode of interest and has a direct influence on the amplitude of the resulting forced response. The modal force is mathematically defined as the product of modal displacement and unsteady pressure integrated over the blade surface, as shown in equations (2) and (3).

$$f_{modal} = \iint \hat{u}_i * (p\hat{n})dA \quad (2)$$

$$f_{modal} = \iint (f_{real} + i * f_{imag})dA \quad (3)$$

The unsteady pressure corresponding to the 44EO and the modal force density are shown in Figures 20 and 21, respectively. At the hub region, the unsteady pressure levels are higher in the GUIde V case near the LE on the pressure side, extending to almost the mid-chord. On the suction side, the pressure levels are higher with a lower pressure level at the leading edge. The most striking difference is evident on the suction side near the trailing edge, where the higher MF extended until 50% chord from the trailing edge. The trailing edge on the pressure side and suction side has an opposite trend, with GUIde 5 having lower and higher MF regions on the respective blade surfaces.

Figure 20: Unsteady pressure for GUIde VI (right) and GUIde V (left)

The computed area integral of the modal force density decreased from 1.03 N to 0.706 N, corresponding to a 31.45% reduction in modal force between the cases. The magnitude of the modal force reduction is consistent with the observed reduction in blade deflection in the experimental data, which was 32.9% including the drop in the measured responses due to axial location shift. The increased MF at the leading edge on suction likely balances the corresponding decrease on the pressure side for in GUIde 6. Therefore, the reduction in the MF between GUIde 5 and GUIde can be primarily attributed to the low MF region at the trailing edge.

Figure 21: Modal Force Density GUIde VI (right) and GUIde V (left)

The similar upstream and downstream counts result in interactions of variations in the flow field caused by minor changes in the ambient inlet conditions. The change in the modal force is, therefore, likely a combination of the reduced loading and aerodynamic clocking.

4.5 Clocking Study

A computational clocking study, as described in Section 3.1, was conducted to investigate the aerodynamic clocking phenomenon by comparing responses across multiple clocking conditions. Previous research on multistage compressors, supported by conclusive experimental measurements, has demonstrated sinusoidal trends in both efficiency and resonant response. The presence of a phase shift in the sinusoidal responses would be an indication of aerodynamic clocking.

The modal forces corresponding to the GUIde V and GUIde VI cases for the six clocking configurations at HL discussed in the previous section are shown in Figure 22. A reduction in the mean value, along with a phase shift, is observed between the GUIde V and GUIde VI cases. In the clocking study, the maximum response occurs at CL0 in GUIde 5 cases and CL3 in GUIde VI cases, while the minimum occurs at CL3 and CL5 for the respective cases. The maximum difference in the mean amplitudes for the clocking conditions is 39.1% for GUIde V and 22.3% for GUIde VI cases.

Figure 22: Modal force for clocking configurations

5. CONCLUSION

The effects of the ambient conditions on rotor resonant response for the same resonant conditions obtained from two separate test campaigns were investigated. Compressor research facilities that draw unconditioned ambient air may exhibit significant variation in the measured response due to changing ambient conditions, despite using a standard day correction procedure to set the loading prior to the speed sweeps needed to collect the vibratory data. In contrast to performance studies, which can account for variations in the inlet conditions by adjusting the rotational speed to match the Mach number by matching the corrected speed, forced response studies are constrained to the resonant speed, leading to differences in the resulting flow field, including flow angles and Mach numbers. These differences become particularly significant when the upstream and downstream vane counts are identical, augmenting the differences through phasing of the upstream and downstream forcing functions.

A 35.2% drop in the mean response amplitude was observed at high loading between the two experimental test campaigns, where the only significant difference occurred with the ambient inlet conditions. A computational study was conducted to investigate the flow physics associated with the change in response behavior for the different inlet conditions. The computational study showed a similar reduction in the modal force.

The changes in the mean peak response amplitude are, therefore, attributed to a combination of changes in the flowfield and aerodynamic clocking. On hot days, the rotor experiences reduced blade loading at resonance due to a change in the corrected speed, accompanied by variations in the incidence angle and Mach number at the adjacent blade rows. Variations in the incidence angles along with convective velocity and Mach number can modify the timing of wake and potential field impingement on the rotor, thus leading to aerodynamic clocking. These mechanisms were verified in the current investigation by

comparing the flowfield between the two cases. These results highlight the importance of considering variations in the flow field that affect forced response studies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kemp, N. H., and Sears, W. R., 1955, "The Unsteady Forces Due to Viscous Wakes in Turbomachines," *Journal of the Aeronautical Sciences*, **22**(7), pp. 478–483. <https://doi.org/10.2514/8.3376>.
- [2] Goldstein, M. E., 1978, "Unsteady Vortical and Entropic Distortions of Potential Flows Round Arbitrary Obstacles," *J. Fluid Mech.*, **89**(3), pp. 433–468. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112078002682>.
- [3] Johnston, R. T., Feiereisen, J. M., and Fleeter, S., 1998, "Measured Rotor Wake and Potential Forcing Functions, Including Blade Row Interactions," *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **14**(2), pp. 191–198. <https://doi.org/10.2514/2.5285>.
- [4] Zhao, B., Yang, C., Hu, L., Zhou, M., and Li, D., 2012, "Investigation of Separating and Utilizing the Influences of Up- and Downstream Blade Rows," *Volume 8: Turbomachinery, Parts A, B, and C*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Copenhagen, Denmark, pp. 2467–2481. <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2012-68371>.
- [5] Hegde, S., Mao, Z., Pan, T., Zori, L., Campregher, R., and Kielb, R., 2019, "Separation of Up and Downstream Forced Response Excitations of an Embedded Compressor Rotor," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **141**(9), p. 091013. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4044212>.
- [6] Sanders, A. J., and Fleeter, S., 2001, "Multi-Blade Row Interactions in a Transonic Axial Compressor: Part II — Rotor Wake Forcing Function and Stator Unsteady Aerodynamic Response," *Volume 4: Manufacturing Materials and Metallurgy; Ceramics; Structures and Dynamics; Controls, Diagnostics and Instrumentation*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, p. V004T03A033. <https://doi.org/10.1115/2001-GT-0269>.
- [7] Sanders, A. J., and Fleeter, S., 2002, "Rotor Blade-to-Blade Wake Variability and Effect on Downstream Vane Response," *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **18**(2), pp. 456–464. <https://doi.org/10.2514/2.5956>.
- [8] Li, H. D., and He, L., 2003, "Blade Count and Clocking Effects on Three-Bladerow Interaction in a Transonic Turbine," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **125**(4), pp. 632–640. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1622711>.

- [9] Mailach, R., and Vogeler, K., 2004, “Rotor-Stator Interactions in a Four-Stage Low-Speed Axial Compressor Part I: Unsteady Profile Pressures and the Effect of Clocking,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **126**, pp. 507–518. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1791641>.
- [10] Hsu, S. T., and Wo, A. M., 1998, “Reduction of Unsteady Blade Loading by Beneficial Use of Vortical and Potential Disturbances in an Axial Compressor with Rotor Clocking,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **120**(4), pp. 705–713. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2841781>.
- [11] Jia, H., Xi, G., Müller, L., Mailach, R., and Vogeler, K., 2010, “Unsteady Blade Loading with Clocking in Multistage Axial Compressors, Part 1,” *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **26**(1), pp. 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.36914>.
- [12] Key, N. L., Lawless, P. B., and Fleeter, S., 2008, “An Investigation of the Flow Physics of Vane Clocking Using Unsteady Flow Measurements,” *Volume 6: Turbomachinery, Parts A, B, and C*, ASME/DC, Berlin, Germany, pp. 2003–2014. <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2008-51091>.
- [13] Besem, F. M., Kielb, R. E., and Key, N. L., 2016, “Forced Response Sensitivity of a Mistuned Rotor From an Embedded Compressor Stage,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **138**(3), p. 031002. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4031866>.
- [14] Key, N. L., Lawless, P. B., and Fleeter, S., 2009, “Vane Clocking in a Three-Stage Compressor: Frequency Domain Data Analysis,” *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **25**(5), pp. 1100–1107. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.43423>.
- [15] Cizmas, P. G. A., and Dorney, D. J., 2000, “The Influence of Clocking on Unsteady Forces of Compressor and Turbine Blades,” *International Journal of Turbo and Jet Engines*, **17**(2). <https://doi.org/10.1515/TJJ.2000.17.2.133>.
- [16] Smith, N. R., and Key, N. L., 2015, “Vane Clocking Effects on Stator Loss for Different Compressor Loading Conditions,” *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **31**(2), pp. 519–526. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.B35193>.
- [17] Müller, L., Mailach, R., Vogeler, K., Jia, H., and Xi, G., 2010, “Unsteady Blade Loading with Clocking in Multistage Axial Compressors, Part 2,” *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **26**(1), pp. 36–45. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.36916>.
- [18] Choi, Y., Key, N., and Fleeter, S., 2008, “Vane Clocking Effects on the Resonant Response of an Embedded Rotor,” *44th AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference & Exhibit*, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Hartford, CT. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2008-4793>.
- [19] Niu, H., Chen, J., and Xiang, H., 2023, “A New Influence Mechanism of Clocking Effect in Subsonic Compressor,” *Applied Sciences*, **13**(18), p. 10094. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app131810094>.
- [20] Smith, N. R., Berdanier, R. A., Fabian, J. C., and Key, N. L., 2015, “Reconciling Compressor Performance Differences for Varying Ambient Inlet Conditions,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **137**(12), p. 122603. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4030518>.
- [21] Kormanik, N. J., Matthews, D. R., Key, N. L., and King, A. J., 2019, “Purdue 3-Stage Axial Compressor Research Facility: Through the Years, to Infinity, and Beyond,” *AIAA Propulsion and Energy 2019 Forum*, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Indianapolis, IN. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2019-4000>.
- [22] Kamdar, N., Lou, F., and Key, N. L., 2021, “Details of Shrouded Stator Hub Cavity Flow in a Multi-Stage Axial Compressor Part 1: Interactions With the Primary Flow,” *Volume 2A: Turbomachinery — Axial Flow Fan and Compressor Aerodynamics*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Virtual, Online. <https://doi.org/10.1115/gt2021-60103>.
- [23] Menter, F. R., 1994, “Two-Equation Eddy-Viscosity Turbulence Models for Engineering Applications,” *AIAA Journal*, **32**(8), pp. 1598–1605. <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.12149>.
- [24] Smirnov, P. E., and Menter, F. R., 2009, “Sensitization of the SST Turbulence Model to Rotation and Curvature by Applying the Spalart–Shur Correction Term,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **131**(4). <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3070573>.
- [25] ANSYS Inc, 2023, “CFX Reference Guide.”
- [26] Brown, J., Kormanik III, N., Matthews, D., and Key, N. L., “Experimental and Computational Analysis of Heat Transfer Effects on the Performance of a Multistage Axial Compressor,” *ETC15: Proceedings of 15th European Conference on Turbomachinery Fluid Dynamics & Thermodynamics*, Budapest, Hungary. <https://doi.org/10.29008/ETC2023-369>.
- [27] Clark, J. P., and Grover, E. A., 2007, “Assessing Convergence in Predictions of Periodic-Unsteady Flowfields,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **129**(4), pp. 740–749. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2720504>.
- [28] Matthews, D. R., and Key, N. L., 2025, “Considerations for High-Fidelity Modeling of Unsteady Flows in a Multistage Axial Compressor,” *IJTPP*, **10**(1), p. 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijtp10010005>.
- [29] Hellmich, B., and Seume, J. R., 2008, “Causes of Acoustic Resonance in a High-Speed Axial Compressor,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **130**(3), p. 031003. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2775487>.